

INTERPRETATION OF THE OGABI NOVEL BY KENGESBOY KARIMOV

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Annotation: *in the article, you will get acquainted with the first book of the novel "Agabiy" by the Karakalpak crusader Kengesboy Karimov, an article in which this and the work are analyzed, and the author's skills, the peculiarities of the work are touched upon*

Key words: *sense, fatal tragedy, remarkable phenomenon, writer, publicist, poet*

Our night today, today tomorrow, the next day of our day will definitely become history is an axiom that does not require comment. Writing a work that tells about the past of an entire nation is tantamount to covering a piece of human history. In this sense, the novel "Agabiy" by Kengesboy Karimov will undoubtedly be sealed as an important and remarkable phenomenon in the history of our literature. We are not mistaken if we say that in the novel "Agabiy", which tells about the recent history, due to the mutual disputes between the seeds of Karakalpak-he is a path of wanderings and a catastrophe that happens unexpectedly in him-he, the consequences of disasters, even fatal tragedy, were skillfully revealed by the teacher writer, publicist and poet Kengesboy Karimov. Looking at the glorious history, it turns out that the Karakalpak people, whose eyes are described as Black, clean-hearted, white-hearted, did not pass the tests from their very beginning. Our esteemed first president Islam Abduganievich Karimov in one of his works said: "When we say Karakalpak, about the peculiarities of this working people, about the qualities that make elni el and yurt, first of all, a people's figure appears before us, who has experienced a lot of suffering, destruction and repression throughout its long history, how many hard roads it has traveled, is resistant and tolerant,

" Looking at the history of fraternal Karakalpak written literature, we can see that from year to year it is getting richer and more perfect with new literary works. The novel "Agabiy" by Kengesbay Karimov, a worthy follower of Tulepbergen Gayipbergenov, who was considered the yalovbardari prose of Karakalpak literature, who endowed the treasury of world literature with his historical novels with rare masterpieces, is truly a magnificent work that tells about the recent history of the karakalpaks (the surroundings of the 1800s). Outstanding writer and critic P. Shermuhammedov noted, " there are many complex aspects of addressing a historical topic. It is necessary for the writer to study in depth the period when he took the pen, to fully reflect on historical reality [2.", we can safely say that the author of the novel made a full-fledged remark to the above requirements. The first part of this work was published in the 2016 issue 11-12 of the magazine "Star of the East", in the 2017 issue 1-2-3 with the translation of Rustam Musurmon. The writer describes the historical events by painting them and instilling in the textual structure and content of the work that the karakalpaks serve among their seeds for internal conflicts, for the seed, for the tribe-tribe to live head-on, for the prospect of mutual discord not for the sake of the nation, for its degradation, crisis, and tries to show this fact through "Not a dry recording of the past, but an exciting painting of events through high artistic skills, raising historical figures to the level of a lively artistic type, the creation of the image of a whole era, the type of ERA in the novel is achieved. That is why the fact of history in the historical novel should grow to the level of artistic truth is considered one of the main conditions". In the novel, a serious conflict that gives impetus to the development of events, sets the heroes in motion, not as a result of external influence, but arises in the face of mutual disagreement. We can see that the events of the novel are described and in the traditional way according to the interpretation of the characters. Each reader, entering the reading of the work, feels that the writer is not only motivated not by incident, but by raising socio-spiritual problems, instilling them in the minds of readers through images, by drawing conclusions from the intelligence of the ancestors, from his mistakes. Master writer copied the historical truth into a work of art without breaking it – he

placed the events of the difficult and tested life paths traveled by the ancestors in accordance with the genre requirements of the novel, for example: "a piece of Karakalpak with the compression of the Kazakh Khans who have lived in Turkestan for a long time was run by jungars and, Fergana, passing by him, sheltered Samarkand and Bukhara, is said to have been poured by Amudarya, the old Land of a group of his grandfathers, who moved to the collar of the island"; or: "biy's house, built on a sandpit, was raised by servants and raised to a camel, waiting for the slave porridge to bring a horse. Looked into the street. The move remained from his father and grandfather. Is it written on the forehead of six elat Karakalpak migrating and landing? Between China and Kipchak Kokand and Bukhara, which he knows, with kenagas, the mangites settle and migrate between Bukhara and Khorezm. By order of the emir, he went to the karakalpaks located on the banks of the secret. This is the situation with them too.

If it moves by the water in summer, it will return to wintering in winter. They do not give their necks to graze and farm. A thoughtful analysis of the historical events embedded in Khiva, such as "Amu Darya's feet are citizens of Khiva, farming around Chimboy, Zangot, Davqora, Lakes at the confluence of the river and the sea heard that those who lost fish and game and feed on cattle", is a clear example. In the process of reading the work, the author's knowledge of history, (the main events of the work in harmony with historical sources) religious knowledge (prayer times to indicate the time of the event and the naming and order of the suras and verses read in it, the indication of deeds that have become strict rules for Muslims through the action of; he strangled the rabbit, saying "bismillo"..."), animal (description and classification of horses in the work, some thoughts about camels, rows about the way of life of wolves, from this phrase "the beirul, who ended up on the forehead of the Erepboy, would ride the horse and take the suck. Good to ride, the zealous boyrul has no speed to run in the race, there is an endurance that is suitable for Capricorn...") and nabotot (some information about several plants, such as ostrich, yavshan, saksovul), from the secrets of folk medicine (mention of methods and elements of natural healing for diseases from the language of heroes), from geographical

knowledge (masterful behavior of heroes in the chapter on protection against the seasons of nature and its whims), it can be seen that he is aware of the science of astronomy (determining the path by looking at the stars and plotting the time), and the fact that he "edirib" each of these by looking at the place that the characters hold on the scale of the novel is also a factor that ensures the methodical originality of the writer.

At this point, the writer, referring to the language of the author and the proverbs, Proverbs, traditions and traditions that are being brought dark, again and again through the speech of the characters, was able to show the National Colorite characteristic of the Karakalpak people in a special way. For example, in the following excerpt from the work from the author's language, a look that has become a natural habit for karakalpaks over the centuries is highlighted:

"- Kishe, did the meat cook?" he said, throwing traps out of his pocket on the ground and separating them from each other.

- Did You Stand, Akjigit? - said the woman back to the answer with the question. She was the mother who gave birth to a tall, white-yellow bride with tender blue eyes, and the child was the only one the bride wished." The mother says "Akjigit" without saying her child's horse until she recognizes Esin in the karakalpaks according to the habit that has come from before, and the child, in turn, calls her mother "kische". Understood from the dialogue of the heroes, both from the content of the short text and from the information of the author who came after it, it turns out that the appeal of mother and child to one of the other peoples is more special than that of other peoples.

Let's focus on the excerpt from the information provided by the Author: "according to the custom that has come from the previous one in karakalpaks..."it seems to us that the work, which continues to look at history due to the fact that it is noted, gives an idea that the situation in this picture was even earlier than in those times. In addition to showing the tradition inherent in the whole nation through dialogue, an emphasis is placed on the mental state of the heroes, that is, the mother's love for the child "the image, essence, inner world of the hero are visible in

dialogues. A skillfully finished dialogue can be compared to Lightning: with it, the hero's being, individual image is instantly illuminated"[3.195].

In addition, the writer used only dialogues to show the identity of the nation, or without special mention of them, instilled in the image of the people. For example, the character of the work showed that Erejeb was old enough by the description of his image-he also indicated by the description. "Erejeb was also a boy who left hivich a horse and fed Haydar kokil's wedding with a circumcision wedding, testifying that his father was being as tall as a slave, reconciling blue eyes on his white-yellow face and dusting his ovul cuttings." Circumcision is considered a practice in the entire Muslim world, which is circumcision for boys. Haydar kokil wedding is a tradition of Karakalpak people, a solemn ceremony that is held from the birth of a boy until reaching the 6th-7th youth to grow hair in the central part of the head without a brush, and when the time comes to trim it according to habits. In addition, the appearance of the aza ceremony in the work is also impressively and vividly cited. "Jurinboy stopped crying and serrated. Then my father, following the order of the karakalpaks coming from time to time, made two bends to the ground and sounded "wow" and walked towards the Black House. The place of the exhausted wound on Bektemir's chest was stabbed by "grass". Staggered. Did not fall.

Jurin entered the Black House and said, "Woe to you", " we lost our mother," and the Earth was kicking and weeping." This tradition, which shows that men, too, express their sympathy through the word, try to bring out the resentment, mediocrity, loss and loss with these "woe", express sympathy for the azadores, is briefly and clearly described in the work. In addition to the traditions, traditions, ritual manifestations associated with the National Colorite, which we noted above, the Odums typical for the Karakalpak people, such as eating in the novel "Agabiy", peculiarities at the beginning of the table, giving permission, travel traditions, hospitality traditions, are shown in parallel with the process of events.

Together with revealing the spirit of the heroes, the author also showed that the Karakalpak people have rich oral creativity. About 100 Proverbs used as early as the first part of the work, more than 50 analogies are a clear example of the

application of saj art, which is widely found in folk epics, and precisely the name of Epics, which are the product of folk oral creativity, the following excerpts about the courage of their heroes. "One of those who dreams of being great, not putting Cablan's lace from the tongue with the Boyarchibor of alpomish, but knocking down a brunette with such a vulture, a sword of a chisel, a web" was this Jurinboy.

– - How do the two of us share everyone? Everyone is one, we are two friends, " said Hakimkul one day.

Although it was really interesting. In the evening at the weddings, in the epics, where the jirovs are ringing, in the "Alpomish", "Cablan", "Göroqli", the leeches touched the most sunken pahlavon. These are the two."In conclusion, we can say that the novel by Kengesboy Karimov "Agabiy" is read fluently and at the same time invites the reader to think, observe, encourages him to send his fantasies on a journey towards Mozy. In the process of reading the work, the reader, together with the pleasure of the work of art, is convinced that it is a source of comprehensive information about the distant and difficult past of the Karakalpak people, about the politics carried out in past times, about sharp word games like swords, about refugees, about the rich traditions of it.

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